

A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF ENVIRONMENTAL EXPENDITURE IN SOUTHERN INDIAN STATES

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INTRODUCTION

Environment generally means surroundings. It is sum total of all the living and non-living elements. Environment supplies services such as land, water, timber, minerals, and fossil fuel which are necessary for economic development. Further it also provides services such as carbon sequestration, water purification, controlling flood risks, soil formation, photosynthesis, pollination, nutrient cycling. Along with these it brings spiritual enrichment, cognitive development, recreation and aesthetic enjoyment. All these show the importance of environment. Such environment is degraded by human activities like deforestation, burning fossil fuel, over population, agriculture, industrialization, urbanization etc. To sustain all forms of living things, we need to protect and preserve environment. In order to protect environment finances are required. In this regard environment finance emerges as new field of enquiry and activity that has grown up to address the challenges of environment.

Environmental Finance is an emerging and rapidly growing interdisciplinary field of research, concerned with the financial implications of environmental change for industries and firms, and the need to transition to a sustainable economy. The field brings together research in finance and the natural sciences to develop financial and market solutions to some of humanity's most pressing concerns; namely, climate change and shifts in other Earth system processes. The modern environmental finance movement appeared in the second half of the nineteenth century in response to the industrial ugliness and destruction of the industrial revolution (Labatt and White, 2002). But in India, the systems for environmental governance and regulation traced back to the Ancient India, around 1700–500 BC, with the Upanishads and Vedas linking the flourishing of civilization to living in harmony with nature. This is also followed by the Indian Emperors, the examples of which can be found in the

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Indian History. For instance, Emperor Chandragupta Maurya is said to have appointed a special officer to protect the forests and to allow the use of forests only for specific purposes, viz. religious study, forest produce, grazing of royal elephants and hunting, while Emperor Ashoka promoted tree plantation along roads and the cultivation of medicinal plants. These practices were re-energized by the notification of the National Forest Act in 1878, which later gave way to the Indian Forest Act, 1927. These environmental concerns were supplemented by the Directive Principles of State Policy, an integral and significant element of Constitution of India, which reflect the commitment of the State to protect the environment with regard to forests and wildlife and which enjoin upon the citizens of India the responsibility to protect and improve the environment.

Matters related to governance of natural resources is allocated to different Ministries of the Government of India, The Ministry of Environment, Forest and Climate Change (MoEF&CC) has been designated as the nodal agency in the Government of India for overseeing the implementation of India's environment and forest policies and programmes relating to conservation of the country's natural resources, its biodiversity, forests and wildlife and for ensuring the welfare of animals and prevention and abatement of pollution. In order to know the concept better, have to understand the definition of environment finance.

According to Sonia Labatt and Rodney R. White "Environmental finance is a recently coined term and was used at the end of the twentieth century. It is a field of inquiry and activity that has grown up to address the challenges of environmental hazards".

Christopher Berendt opined Environmental finance includes finance on forest, soil conservation, water supply and sanitation, plantation, reducing air pollution, water purification and animal conservation.

Dr. Jurg P. Blum defined the term "Environmental finance as a fairly new field, covering mainly with finance and investment regarding ecological environment".

According to Environment Financing Accounting report "Environmental Finance deals with accounting for and reporting on environmental transactions events that effect financial position and performance of an enterprise".

Review of Literature

Mathur (1998) conducted study on public expenditure on water supply. It focuses on the role of state governments i.e., Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka, Maharashtra, Tamil Nadu in providing safe drinking water and sanitation facilities which effects environment. For this it has collected the data from budget papers and finance accounts of state governments. It has

concluded that vast irrigation potential has been created in the states over the past four decades. The greater emphasis is being placed on the better and future utilization of the already created irrigation infrastructure rather than creation of additional infrastructure. The key suggestions were that 10 percent of plan investment be set aside for major and medium irrigation projects and efforts be directed to involve the private sector.

The JBIC report, 2001 identified in the Indian context, the environment is being affected by economic activities. The effect of environmental degradation is not only in urban but also in rural areas. The government has the third Tier that is capable of encountering and introducing schemes for environmental infrastructure. The third Tier consists of 2,30,000 local, and 5900 intermediate, and 499 districts panchayats. Further, the study highlights the autonomous institutes like 8300 village councils, 25 block advisory councils, and 16 autonomous development agencies. Further, the nation has 96 municipal corporations, 1500 municipalities, and 2090 Nagar Panchayat to preserve the environment at the basic levels.

Environmental Financial Advisory Board (2010) report submits the concern over water and air quality in India due to green gas emission. The report demands establishing and financing sources to improve the quality by reducing green gas omissions in the sphere. The report initiates several programs that aim at the central and domestic level with financing the installation of energy-efficient and environment improvement devices at government offices, schools, public places, and non-government organizations. The report also highlights that the clean water state revolving fund (CWSRF) has touched over \$75 billion. The drinking water state revolving fund (DWSRF) is \$15 billion worth and continuously working in the areas of concern. The report concludes with advice to set up a financing initiative to control air quality and non-point source water.

Barman and Gupta (2010) studied public expenditure, environment, and economic growth from the Indian perspective. The article develops an efficient relationship between the three. The paper provides an insight on the positive relation between government expenditure towards environment improves the public productivity. The study further explores the uneven allocation of tax collection towards environment spending concerns.

Objectives

1. Comparative analysis of public expenditure on environment in major south Indian states i.e. Karnataka, Kerala, Andhra Pradesh and Tamil Nadu.

Methodology

The article aims at comparative analysis of public expenditure on environment in major south Indian states i.e Karnataka, Kerala, Andhra Pradesh and Tamil Nadu. Secondary data of public expenditure on environment with respective states for twenty years are collected from RBI state finance (Total environment expenditure includes expenses on water supply and sanitation, agriculture and allied sector, irrigation and flood control, science, technology and environment). Collected data mined using excel.

Analysis

Environmental Finance is an emerging and rapidly growing interdisciplinary field of research, concerned with the financial implications of environmental change for industries and firms, and the need to transition to a sustainable economy. Expenditure towards the environment development and upliftment expenses of the South Indian states has been studied.

The expenditure towards environment has been an important area of the decade. The maintenance, development and upliftment of the environment has been priority of the many governments. Total environmental revenue expenditure of various states (Current price) over the two decades of Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka, Kerala, and Tamil Nadu is presented in table 1. It can be observed that, Andhra Pradesh government's spending has increased from Rs. 2873.70 crores to Rs. 23100.67 crores, with least amount in 2015-16 as a result of separation of Telangana from Andhra Pradesh. Karnataka state has spent Rs. 2305.54 crores to Rs. 27189.62 crores, Kerala has spent Rs. 1076.27 crores to Rs. 9146.03 crores and Tamil Nadu has spent Rs. 1970.96 crores to Rs. 15763.55 crores respectively. Total environment revenue expenditure of Andhra Pradesh and Karnataka are higher as compared to that of the other states due to large region (Ministry of statistics and programme implementation). The revenue expenditure includes spending on administrative, operations and maintenance expenditure (payment of salaries, travel and other expenses, interest payment etc.) of various environment conservation, preservation, control authorities, institutions and boards, national parks and wild life sanctuaries, cost of social and farm forestry, environment education and training, environment research centers, disaster management authority, eco restoration works, waste treatment and disposal, access to drinking water, preservation and control of pollution, subsidies that help to improve stock of forests, forest cleaning and re-forestation and environmental monitoring etc.

Table 1: Revenue expenditure on environment of south Indian States

Year	Total Environment Revenue Expenditure of various states (Current price) (Rs. In Crores)			
	Andhra Pradesh	Karnataka	Kerala	Tamil Nadu
2000-01	2873.70	2305.54	1076.27	1970.96
2001-02	2816.69	1715.52	988.99	1950.14
2002-03	3277.38	1786.75	1173.80	2226.28
2003-04	3576.42	2238.70	1172.50	2327.51
2004-05	3814.97	2826.13	1551.64	3050.84
2005-06	5156.13	3721.19	1484.43	3434.34
2006-07	6359.18	4238.27	1670.94	2519.72
2007-08	8358.28	5171.25	1810.89	2944.18
2008-09	9558.63	4157.58	2265.46	4840.73
2009-10	9939.66	6623.31	2582.82	4232.34
2010-11	11018.36	5598.67	2986.74	5414.29
2011-12	12765.85	6617.65	4069.44	5759.10
2012-13	14941.05	9474.79	5163.82	7334.86
2013-14	15236.06	14450.11	5298.54	9519.71
2014-15	17644.98	13722.55	5664.88	9433.13
2015-16	7720.09	17313.14	6614.91	12765.17
2016-17	10875.82	21005.03	7589.11	15009.68
2017-18	13051.63	22463.51	7346.55	15259.89
2018-19*	12168.74	24126.71	11012.02	18233.36
2019-20*	23100.67	27189.62	9146.03	15763.55

Source: RBI State Finance, <https://rbi.org.in/>

Table 2: Capital expenditure on environment of south Indian States

Year	Total Environment Capital Expenditure of various states (Current price) (Rs. In Crores)			
	Andhra Pradesh	Karnataka	Kerala	Tamil Nadu
2000-01	1305.11	1367.80	198.72	886.21
2001-02	1470.55	1605.19	178.36	924.34
2002-03	1983.85	2088.92	180.6	836.95
2003-04	1909.72	2004.14	197.73	784.74
2004-05	4037.57	3252.80	208.37	1725.72
2005-06	6167.03	4066.94	252.06	830.55
2006-07	8236.98	4717.33	257.34	2288.26
2007-08	11109.34	4499.53	291.18	2553.04
2008-09	8590.58	4196.98	381.96	2640.63
2009-10	11531.94	5132.20	611.53	2490.76
2010-11	9327.59	5877.55	759.37	2262.27
2011-12	11018.90	7364.48	668.02	3971.45
2012-13	10885.02	6763.54	654.54	3697.53
2013-14	10006.62	7589.49	649.85	3052.31
2014-15	4464.20	9265.52	743.52	3569.63
2015-16	9065.72	7562.72	1139.14	3461.82
2016-17	10681.91	9564.65	1741.79	3367.70
2017-18	9048.63	11160.57	1565.97	2917.46
2018-19*	14177.27	14284.46	2357.13	4738.83
2019-20*	13540.86	16390.09	1986.68	7437.27

Source: RBI State Finance, <https://rbi.org.in/>

Table 2 illustrates total environment capital expenditure of Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka, Kerala, and Tamil Nadu at current prices. Establishment of national parks, sanctuaries, upgradation, re-forestation of forest areas also requires machineries, land, building etc. that require capital outlay. In addition, activities like forestry, expansion of forest areas, towards building national parks or updating the existing and construction of mini-irrigation like check

dam activities for groundwater recharge also need capital expenditures. It can be inferred that; Andhra Pradesh government has spent Rs. 1305.11 crores to Rs. 13540.86 crores while Karnataka has spent Rs. 1367.80 crores to Rs. 16390.09 crores, Kerala spent Rs. 198.72 crores to Rs. 1986.686 crores and Tamil Nadu has spent Rs. 886.21 crores to Rs. 7437.27 crores during study period. It is noticeable that, amongst all Karnataka government has spent highest followed by Andhra Pradesh, Tamil Nadu and Kerala. It can be attributed to establishment of Centre for Environment Education (2002), 64 soil testing labs and 2 solar parks (Pavagada and Kasaragodu), new wildlife sanctuaries (Bhimgad and Dandeli), wind energy, and ecological parks in these twenty years.

Table 3: Total environment expenditure of south Indian States (current prices)

Year	Total Environmental Expenditure of various states (in current prices) (Rs. In Crores)			
	Andhra Pradesh	Karnataka	Kerala	Tamil Nadu
2000-01	4178.81	3673.34	1274.99	2857.17
2001-02	4287.24	3320.71	1167.35	2874.48
2002-03	5261.23	3875.67	1354.4	3063.23
2003-04	5486.14	4242.84	1370.23	3112.25
2004-05	7852.54	6078.93	1760.01	4776.56
2005-06	11323.16	7788.13	1736.49	4264.89
2006-07	14596.16	8955.6	1928.28	4807.98
2007-08	19467.62	9670.78	2102.07	5497.22
2008-09	18149.21	8354.56	2647.42	7481.36
2009-10	21471.6	11755.51	3194.35	6723.1
2010-11	20345.95	11476.22	3746.11	7676.56
2011-12	23784.75	13982.13	4737.46	9730.55
2012-13	25826.07	16238.33	5818.36	11032.39
2013-14	25242.68	22039.6	5948.39	12572.02
2014-15	22109.18	22988.07	6408.4	13002.76
2015-16	16785.81	24875.86	7754.05	16226.99
2016-17	21557.73	30569.68	9330.9	18377.38
2017-18	22100.26	33624.075	8912.532	18177.35

Year	Total Environmental Expenditure of various states (in current prices) (Rs. In Crores)			
	Andhra Pradesh	Karnataka	Kerala	Tamil Nadu
2018-19*	26346.02	38411.167	13369.15	22972.19
2019-20*	36641.53	43579.717	11132.72	23200.82
CAGR (%)	11.47	13.16	11.44	11.04
AAGR (%)	13.76	14.87	13.11	12.66
CV	50.14	75.95	76.77	67.90

Source: RBI State Finance, <https://rbi.org.in/>

The environment and related activities are broadly classified under five heads i.e., agriculture and allied activities, water supply and sanitation, irrigation (major and minor) and flood control and drainage, science technology and environment, relief on account of natural calamities. Agriculture and allied activities include expenditure on soil and water conservation, forest and wildlife activities, plantation, organic farming and organic manure, soil testing, good quality seeds, etc. Irrigation (major and minor) and flood control and drainage have direct effect on environment. Water supply and sanitation result in ground water variation and cleanliness of environment. Science technology and environment, includes investments on biotechnology, research into new methods of generating power and electricity, new system of handling hazardous wastes. Investment on relief on account of natural calamities helps to rebuild or restore the deteriorated environment. The expenditure on these activities is considered as total environment expenditure. Total environment expenditure of south Indian States at current prices is indicated in Table 3. It can be witnessed that the total environment expenditure of Andhra Pradesh has increased from Rs. 4178.81crores to Rs. 36641.53crores while Karnataka Rs. 3673.34crores to Rs. 43579.71crores, Kerala Rs.1274.99crores to Rs. 11132.72crores and Tamil Nadu from Rs. 2857.17crores to Rs. 23200.82crores during the two decades.

The cumulative abnormal growth rate of all the state is over 11% indicating the states have increased their expenditure by 11% in these years. Karnataka government's spending in these twenty years has been highest as CAGR is over 13 per cent highest as compared to all other south Indian states. Also, on an average growth rate is over 13% by the three states except Tamil Nadu. It can be noticed that average growth rate is higher for Karnataka state

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due to establishment of Western Ghat Task Force to conserve biodiversity in Karnataka and established 5000 village forest committees to increase forest area in Karnataka. More focus of Karnataka government towards organic farming (70,000 hectares of land adopted organic farming), announcement of 'Eco Budget' by Karnataka government to compensate the negative effects of created on forests by humans and introduction of Blue-Plastic management Scheme with Rs. 840 crores to address the issues of plastics polluting water resources in coastal areas. The coefficient of variation found to be over 50 in all the states with highest in Kerala. This points to state's increased variation in spending towards environment development activities over the years.

Graphical representation of Total environment expenditure of South Indian States in constant prices were shown in Figure 1. It can be observed that there has been constant growth in expenditure by the Kerala government. The growth rate is identified at 6.93 per cent CAGR. The similar phenomenon was also observed with minor fluctuations in Tamil Nadu and Karnataka states. Both have grown at a rate of 8.58 per cent and 6.54 per cent over the twenty years. Andhra Pradesh has been highly fluctuating and witnessed downward trend in the mid years due to separation of Telangana. The state recorded an average growth rate of 8.85% and CAGR of 6.95%.

Figure 1: Total environment expenditure of South Indian States (in constant prices)

Total environment expenditure of south Indian states at constant prices is recorded in Table 4. The Table also reveals that, over the two decades at constant prices, Karnataka government has shown highest CGAR growth of 8.58% followed by Andhra Pradesh (6.95%), Kerala (6.93%), and least was witnessed in Tamil Nadu (6.54%). The average annual growth rate was also found to be in line with CAGR with highest being Karnataka state i. e., 10.02% followed by Andhra Pradesh (8.85%), Kerala (8.25%), and Tamil Nadu (7.80%) indicating a long-term growth trend with a growth rate of over 7% increase in annual expenditure on an annual basis by the respective state governments.

Table 4: Total environment expenditure of South Indian States(in constant prices)

Year	Total Environmental Expenditure of various states (in constant prices) (Rs. In Crores)			
	Andhra Pradesh	Karnataka	Kerala	Tamil Nadu
2000-01	7847.02	6897.84	2394.19	5365.23
2001-02	7771.13	6019.18	2115.96	5210.33
2002-03	9222.14	6793.47	2374.06	5369.38
2003-04	9118.88	7052.31	2277.55	5173.08
2004-05	12257.81	9489.21	2747.38	7456.21
2005-06	16914.31	11633.75	2593.93	6370.81
2006-07	20452.97	12549.09	2702.02	6737.21
2007-08	26062.57	12946.90	2814.18	7359.49
2008-09	22484.85	10350.37	3279.86	9268.57
2009-10	25624.75	14029.32	3812.22	8023.52
2010-11	22163.31	12501.31	4080.72	8362.25
2011-12	23784.75	13982.13	4737.46	9730.55
2012-13	24159.09	15190.21	5442.81	10320.29
2013-14	22437.94	19590.76	5287.46	11175.13
2014-15	19411.04	20182.68	5626.34	11415.94
2015-16	15301.56	22676.26	7068.41	14792.15
2016-17	19316.96	27392.19	8361.02	16467.19
2017-18	19234.34	29263.77	7756.77	15820.14
2018-19*	21991.67	32062.74	11159.56	19175.45

Year	Total Environmental Expenditure of various states (in constant prices) (Rs. In Crores)			
	Andhra Pradesh	Karnataka	Kerala	Tamil Nadu
2019-20*	30083.36	35779.73	9140.16	19048.29
CAGR (%)	6.95	8.58	6.93	6.54
AAGR (%)	8.85	10.02	8.25	7.80
CV	34.93	54.64	55.39	45.37

Source: RBI State Finance, <https://rbi.org.in/>

Conclusion:

Government expenditure towards environmental management and development is an area of interest to many researchers and academicians. The governments of various states have been allocating large amount of their capital towards environment preservation, development and maintenance. The South Indian states too were one among the caring for better future. It is observed that, all the firms have been investing in building environmental infrastructure through allocating a large portion of their budget. Highest allocation was by Karnataka government i.e., 10.02 per cent over the year while least by Tamil Nadu (7.85%). The compounded annual growth rate of Karnataka state was found to be highest i.e., 8.58% while Kerala government's spending was least.

During twenty years' time period South Indian States have given special preference to environment protection. The individual government's according to their requirement carve out various programs and schemes and allocate the resources. In overall it can be concluded that, the four states with special emphasis of total environment expenditure shows; Andhra Pradesh environment expenditure has increased over three-fold with an initial increasing trend; five-fold increase in environment expenses was found during the two decades by Karnataka government with a steady increasing trend; Kerala witnessed three-fold increase and a steady increasing trend with a decline at the end and Tamil Nadu witnessed three-fold increase in environment building expenses with an increasing trend at constant price.

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